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“IN VITRO EVALUATION OF ANTHELMINTIC ACTIVITY OF JUICE OF *EUPHORBIA LIGULARIA ROXB.*”

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ABSTRACT

The aim of present study was to evaluate anthelmintic potential of the juice of *Euphorbia ligularia* using *Pheretima posthuma* and *Ascaridia galli* as test worms. Various concentrations (10 – 100 mg/ml) of juice were tested in the bioassay, which involved determination of time of paralysis (P) and time of death (D) of the worms. Piperazine citrate (10 mg/ml) was included as standard reference and distilled water as control. The results of present study indicated that juice significantly demonstrated paralysis, and also caused death of worms especially at higher concentration of 100 mg/ml, as compared to standard reference Piperazine citrate. In conclusion, the *E. ligularia* juice as an anthelmintic have been confirmed.

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INTRODUCTION

The relation between the man and the nature dates back to the age old existence of man himself. Since the dawn of civilization, nature has continued to awe man with its abundant surprise. From the varied plants and their enumerable uses, every substance in nature has aroused man's curiosity to many folds. The WHO has estimated that 80% of the world's population already relies on traditional medicine for their primary healthcare needs, therefore traditional medical plants being an important component of complementary and alternative medicine may be useful for drug discovery and development¹.

Euphorbia ligularia is a shrub of height 2 to 5 meters. In the satpuda range the juice of *E. ligularia* is use for the treatment of asthma, fever, cough and worm removing process in small children etc. In satpuda region special treatment is given to the stem before collecting the juice.

Soil-transmitted helminth (STH) infections are among the most prevalent of chronic human infections worldwide². Helminthes are generally restricted to tropical regions and cause serious problems to health and contribute to the prevalence of undernourishment, anemia, eosinophilia and pneumonia³. Parasitic diseases caused by helminthes lead to significant health hazards to animals resulting in enormous economic impact. While a number of anthelmintics are currently available, all are encountering resistance. The Juice shows presence of tannins and tannins shows anthelmintic activities⁴. The objective of this work was to evaluate *in vitro* the anthelmintic activity of juice obtained from *Euphorbia ligularia* against *Pheretima posthuma* and *Ascaridia galli*.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Plant material

The stem of plants were collected from Adawad village Tal: Chopda, Dist Jalgaon (Maharashtra) Plants was authenticated by the Pharmacognosy Dept, MAEER's Maharashtra Institute of Pharmacy, Pune

Extraction of Juice

Stem was covered by wheat dough and heated for half hour with twenty cow dungs. After cooling stem was removed from the dough. It was squeezed to obtain the juice.

Worms Collection and Authentication

Indian earthworm *Pheretima posthuma* of about 5-7 cm long were collected from logged area of soil, from Pune region (MS) and *Ascaridia galli* (Nematode) worms were obtained from freshly slaughtered fowls (*Gallus gallus*).

Preparation of Test Sample

Samples for *in-vitro* study were prepared by dissolving 1 gm of juice in 25 ml of distilled water to obtain a stock solution of 100 mg/ml. From this stock solution, different working dilutions were prepared to get concentration range of 10, 50 and 100 mg/ml.

Anthelmintic Assay

The anthelmintic assay was carried as per the method of Ajaiyeoba E.O. et al⁵ with minor modifications. The assay was performed on adult Indian earthworm, *Pheretima posthuma* due to its anatomical and physiological resemblance with the intestinal roundworm parasite of human beings⁶⁻⁹. Because of easy availability, earthworms have been used widely for the initial evaluation of anthelmintic compounds *in vitro*¹⁰⁻¹³. *Ascaridia galli* worms are easily and plentifully available from freshly slaughtered fowls and its use, as a suitable model for screening of anthelmintic drug was advocated earlier¹⁴⁻¹⁶. 50 ml formulations containing three different concentrations, Juice (10, 50 and 100 mg/ml in distilled water) were prepared and six worms (same type) were placed in it. This was done for both types of worm. Time for paralysis was noted when no movement of any sort could be observed except when the worms were shaken vigorously. Time for death of worms were recorded after ascertaining that the worms neither moved when shaken vigorously nor when dipped in warm water (50 °C). Piperazine citrate (10 mg/ml) was used as reference standard while distilled water as the control.

Table 1: Anthelmintic activity of Juice of *Euphorbia ligularia*.

Sample	Concentration mg/ml	Time taken for Paralysis (P) and Death (D) of worms in minute			
		<i>P. posthuma</i>		<i>A. galli</i>	
		P	D	P	D
Piperazine citrate	10	23± 0.6	54 ± 0.4	15 ± 0.6	29 ± 0.7
Juice	10	25 ± 0.4	50 ± 0.2	21 ± 0.3	35 ± 0.4
Juice	50	22 ± 0.4	34 ± 0.2	13 ± 0.2	30 ± 0.5
Juice	100	15 ± 0.4	36 ± 0.3	12 ± 0.4	21 ± 0.2
Control		>180	>180	>180	>180

All values represent Mean ± SEM; n=6 in each group. Control worms were alive up to 24 hrs of observation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As shown in Table 1, the juice exhibited anthelmintic activity in dose-dependant manner giving shortest time of paralysis (P) and death (D) with 100 mg/ml concentration, for both types of worms. The paralysis of 15 min and time of death of 36 min against the earthworm *P. posthuma* was observed. The reference drug Piperazine citrate showed the same at 23 and 54min, respectively.

Ascaridia galli worms were also shown sensitivity to the juice significantly higher concentration of 100 mg/ml. The juice caused paralysis at 12 min. and time of death of 21 min. Piperazine citrate exhibited similar effects at 15 and 29 min. respectively. The juice of *E. ligularia* shows presence of tannins which are polyphenolic compounds. Some synthetic phenolic anthelmintics e.g. niclosamide, oxyclozanide, bithionol etc., are reported to interfere with energy generation in helminth parasites by uncoupling oxidative phosphorylation¹⁷.

It is possible that tannins contained in the juice produced similar effects. Another possible anthelmintic effect of tannins is that they can bind to free proteins in the gastrointestinal tract of host animal¹⁸ or glycoprotein on the cuticle of the parasite¹⁹ and may cause death.

CONCLUSION

Euphorbia ligularia juice showed anthelmintic activity. However dose and form in which they can be used requires standardization. Future scope involves isolation of phytoconstituents responsible for activity.

Abbreviations

STH: Soil-transmitted helminth

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